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DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW BIOSTRATIGRAPHIC SUBDIVISION OF JURASSIC DEPOSITS IN THE EASTERN PART OF THE NORTH USTYURT BASIN BASED ON PLANT IMPRESSIONS

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***Abstract:** The article examines a new scheme for the biostratigraphic subdivision of Jurassic deposits in the eastern part of the North Ustyurt Basin. Until now, the existing biostratigraphic scheme had a local character. It did not include stratigraphic units such as layers, beds, formations, and horizons. The previously developed biostratigraphic scheme was subdivided only to the stage level, which does not comply with the requirements of the International Stratigraphic Code. A refined biostratigraphic scheme has been developed based on data related to plant impressions, meeting the requirements of the International Stratigraphic Code and the International ESG Standard.*

***Keywords:** Jurassic, reservoir, basin, plant impressions, horizon, section, research, refinement, deposits, boundaries.*

Introduction: Based on the State Program and regulatory legal documents, the geological industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan has identified, for the period up to 2030, a priority objective of achieving a measurable reduction in the industrial “carbon footprint,” as well as implementing projects aimed at meeting WTO requirements and eliminating technical barriers in product manufacturing. Under these objectives, oil and gas producers in the country share a common goal: achieving decarbonization targets through the adoption of international standards in business practices and production management. The international ESG standard has recently become a mandatory requirement for participation in the global system of responsible investment and effective business management [10]. The International Stratigraphic Code is also an international standard that links the age of geological periods with orthostratigraphic groups of fauna and flora. International requirements and rules exist for the identification of such orthostratigraphic groups of fauna and flora.

Jurassic deposits of the Ustyurt oil and gas-bearing region represent one of the key objects for studying the hydrocarbon potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The territory of Northern and Central Ustyurt, within Karakalpakstan, has for several decades been an area of active exploration aimed at identifying and mapping stratigraphic schemes as well as reservoirs associated with continental complexes. The first Jurassic stratigraphic schemes for the region were developed in the mid-20th century and formed the basis for subsequent studies; however, their application revealed significant discrepancies between geophysical markers and stratigraphic boundaries (Fig. 1). This led to differing interpretations of geological sections and ambiguous correlation of productive horizons. Subsequently, new subdivision schemes based on paleontological studies were proposed, which made it possible to refine stratigraphic limits; nevertheless, they did not fully resolve issues related to the identification of smaller stratigraphic units such as horizons, formations, layers, and reservoirs [2,9].

The current level of research, involving the integrated use of lithofacies, paleontological, and geophysical data, opens new opportunities for a more detailed biostratigraphic subdivision of Jurassic deposits [1,3,4,5,6,7].

In 2014, the Kazan–Golovkinsky Stratigraphic Meeting was held in Kazan, during which the following issues related to Jurassic deposits were discussed: the Jurassic–Cretaceous boundary, facies and formations of Jurassic deposits, twofold subdivision of stages (Callovian–Oxfordian, Kimmeridgian–Tithonian), as well as orthostratigraphic plant impressions in Jurassic deposits. Taking these issues into account, M.Kh. Iskandarov, together with specialists from IGIRNIGM, developed a new scheme for the biostratigraphic subdivision of Jurassic deposits in the Aral–Ustyurt region [6]. In 2023, this scheme was published as a monograph (see Figs. 2 and 3).

This biostratigraphic subdivision has been recognized and adopted by international specialists, including Doctor of Geological and Mineralogical Sciences Klara Giorgi of the Azerbaijan–French University (France), in their scientific and applied studies. This is particularly important in view of the need to refine the boundaries between the Lower, Middle, and Upper Jurassic subdivisions and to identify productive levels of industrial significance. The new biostratigraphic scheme will improve the reliability of section correlation, optimize exploration activities, and provide a more robust basis for mapping seismic reflecting horizons in order to prepare structures for deep drilling within the Jurassic deposits of the Ustyurt region (Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. Seismostratigraphic scheme of Jurassic deposits in the eastern part of the North Ustyurt Basin.
 (Compiled by: M.Kh., Iskandarov, O.U. Asatilla, 2026.)

Fig. 2. Correlation scheme for deeply buried wells Karakum-1, Kyzyl-Shaly-1p, Yuksalish-1, and Arka-Kungrad-1p.

(Compiled by A.S., M.Kh. Iskandarov., 2026.)

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Fig. 3. New biostratigraphic scheme of Jurassic deposits in the Ustyurt region based on studies by various authors conducted in different years.

(Compiled by: M.Kh. Iskandarov, 2023.)

Main Part. The significance of this study is determined by the development and refinement of a new biostratigraphic scheme required for the geological substantiation of Jurassic deposits in the eastern part of the North Ustyurt Basin. At present, a biostratigraphic scheme adopted in the early 2000s is still in use; however, it has a local character. The subdivision of sections was carried out only to the stage level, without consideration of layers, beds, formations, and horizons. Such a subdivision did not fully comply with the requirements of the International Stratigraphic Code.

The biostratigraphic scheme proposed by the authors has been refined using new data obtained from the eastern part of the North Ustyurt Basin, specifically from well No. 102 of the Urga field, located on the Kuanysh–Koskaly Ridge, and from well No. 13 of the West Kuyi–Surgil field, associated with the Berdakh Ridge. Within the studied sections, eight formations have been identified:

1. Ergozinskaya Formation – Toarcian Stage, Lower Jurassic;
2. Lower Shakhpakhtinskaya Subformation – Aalenian Stage, Middle Jurassic;
3. Upper Shakhpakhtinskaya Subformation – Bajocian Stage, Middle Jurassic. In the proposed scheme, both subformations are combined into the Shakhpakhtinskaya Formation of the Middle Jurassic;
4. Sarydiirmen Formation – Bathonian Stage, Middle Jurassic;
5. Sudochinskaya Formation – Callovian Stage, Middle Jurassic;
6. Shordzhinskaya Formation – Oxfordian Stage, Upper Jurassic;
7. Nikolaevskaya Formation – Kimmeridgian Stage, Upper Jurassic;
8. Aibugirskaya Formation – Lower Tithonian Stage, Upper Jurassic.

In addition, two productive horizons have been identified: the Berdakh Horizon (an analogue of the Akchalak-4 horizon) and the Kuanysh-3 Horizon. Structural maps have been constructed for these horizons, and new prospective objects have been identified. Their geological age was determined using the method of monographic study of plant impressions, in accordance with the requirements of the International Stratigraphic Code and the international ESG standard.

The Urga field is located in the northeastern part of the Kuanysh–Koskaly Ridge of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, within the former Aral Sea basin. Tectonically, it is situated in the eastern marginal part of the Sudochy Trough, northwest of the Dali field.

A significant number of deep wells have been drilled within the Urga field, intersecting prospective hydrocarbon accumulations in Upper, Middle, and Lower Jurassic deposits [2,9]. Core sampling and production geophysical logging (well logging) were conducted in gas-saturated reservoirs in these wells (see Fig. 5).

Subdivision of the oil and gas-bearing complex and identification of individual beds based on well-logging data were carried out by the authors using radioactive (gamma-ray logging) and electrical methods (spontaneous polarization, SP) (see Figs. 2, 4).

The section is composed of Middle Jurassic deposits and consists of terrigenous rocks represented by interbedding of mudstones, dense sandstones, siltstones, coals, clays, and clayey sandstones [5,6].

In recent years, as a result of extensive geological exploration in the Ustyurt region—including wells No. 1 and 2 of the Kuyi-Shege area, Urga well No. 102, and West Kuyi–Surgil well No. 13—a substantial amount of paleobotanical material has been collected from numerous exploration wells (see Tables 1 and 2).

The collected material is predominantly represented by plant impressions. Their monographic study, supplemented by analysis of archived and published data, made it possible to significantly refine and expand the taxonomic composition of the regional flora. This, in turn, allowed a more detailed characterization of the identified stratigraphic units and clarification of their boundaries [5]. As a result, new data on Jurassic vegetation were obtained, and its association with specific stratigraphic horizons was established (see Figs. 1–4).

Well No. 102 of the Urga field reached a depth of 4200 m; core sampling was carried out down to depths of 3926–3927 m. Lithological descriptions of the core were performed for the intervals 2872–2890 m, and for the Middle Jurassic intervals 3096–3100 m, 3100–3129 m, 3129.8–3144.6 m,

3919–3925 m, and 3926–3927 m. The intervals 2876–2882 m and 3135.8–3139.8 m are predominantly composed of dark-gray to nearly black mudstones. It is within these intervals that a rich assemblage of plant remains was discovered, including *Coniopteris cf. hymenophylloides* (Brongn.) Sew., *C. spectabilis* Bric., *Nilssonina vittaeformis* Prynada, *Nilssonina formosa* Vachrameeva et Vasina, and *Podozamites cf. lanceolatus* (L. et H.) var. *intermedius* Heer, corresponding to Middle Jurassic (Bathonian–Callovian) deposits (see Tables 1, 2).

Petrophysical studies of rocks from the Urga field indicate that highly permeable reservoirs are located in deeply buried parts of the section. Sandy interbeds in well sections may be repeatedly duplicated, creating the illusion of increased bed thickness as a result of deformation. This observation is confirmed by the presence of marker plant impressions. Petrophysical studies conducted in well No. 102 of the Urga field support this conclusion. The obtained results are of considerable importance, as they enable prediction of the development of thick sandy interbeds in the interwell space during data interpretation.

Fig. 4. Correlation scheme of wells Karakum No. 1, Kyzyl-Shaly No. 1p, Yuksalish No. 1p, Arka-Kungrad No. 1p, and Urga No. 102 based on the new biostratigraphic subdivision. (Compiled by: M.Kh. Iskandarov, 2025.)

Fig. 5. Production-geological cross-section of the Urga area, Well No. 102, for the Middle (a) and Lower (b) Jurassic.

(Compiled by: M.Kh. Iskandarov.)

The West Kuyi–Surgil field is administratively located within the Aral Sea area, approximately 45 km northwest of the city of Muynak and about 120 km northwest of the Kungrad station. Tectonically, it is confined to the eastern flank of the Sudochy Trough, situated northwest of the Berdakh field and east of the Surgil field.

Within the studied area, a significant number of deep wells have been drilled, intersecting prospective hydrocarbon accumulations in Upper, Middle, and Lower Jurassic deposits [2,9]. A comprehensive suite of production geophysical logging (well logging) was carried out in the wells, and core samples were collected from gas- and oil-bearing intervals of the section [8].

Correlation of well-logging data during the identification of calcareous sandstone reservoirs was primarily based on comparison using a well-defined marker—the top of the Kimmeridgian Stage. Deposits of this stage throughout the section are characterized by a distinctive electrical log signature and elevated radioactivity values.

In well No. 13 of the West Kuyi–Surgil field, gravelly sandstones were identified at the intervals 4180–4181 m, 4278–4279 m, and 4280–4281 m. These sandstones are characterized by high porosity and permeability, and commercial gas inflows were recorded within these horizons (see Fig. 6).

Well No. 13 of the West Kuyi–Surgil field was drilled to a depth of 4500 m, and core samples were taken from the corresponding intervals. Detailed bed-by-bed lithological descriptions of the core were performed for the intervals 4024–4025 m, 4027–4028 m, 4177–4178 m, 4180–4181 m, 4278–4279 m, and 4280–4281 m. The intervals 4024–4025 m and 4027–4028 m are mainly composed of dark-gray to nearly black, horizontally bedded siltstones with interbeds of black mudstones. In the middle part of the layer, carbonized plant impressions up to 5 cm in length, along with woody remains, were observed within the mudstones (4027.92–4028 m).

The study of plant impressions in well No. 13 of the West Kuyi–Surgil field conducted by M.Kh. Iskandarov showed that the impressions are mainly represented by remains of *Nilssonia vittaeformis* Briq, *Podozamites* sp., and *Phoenicopsis* sp. (Fig. 6). These taxa have been recorded in

the western spurs of the Gissar Range, the Fergana Valley (Uzbekistan), the Caucasus, Ukraine, and France, within Middle Jurassic (Bajocian–Bathonian) deposits.

Fig. 6. Production–geological cross-section of the West Kuyi–Surgil field, well No. 13, for the Lower Jurassic.

(Compiled by: M.Kh. Iskandarov, A.S. Muminov)

Studies of plant impressions and their monographic analysis at the West Kuyi–Surgil field (well No. 13) showed that the impressions are mainly represented by remains of *Nilssonia vittaeformis* Brik, *Podozamites* sp., and *Phoenicopsis* sp., corresponding to Middle Jurassic (Bajocian–Bathonian) deposits (Table 1).

In well No. 102 of the Urga field, plant impressions were investigated and subjected to monographic analysis in the intervals 2876–2882 m and 3135.8–3139.8 m. A rich assemblage of plant remains was identified, including *Coniopteris* cf. *hymenophylloides* (Brongn.) Sew., *C. spectabilis* Bric., *Nilssonia vittaeformis* Prynada, *Nilssonia formosa* Vachrameeva et Vasina, and *Podozamites* cf. *lanceolatus* (L. et H.) var. *intermedius* Heer, corresponding to Middle Jurassic (Bathonian–Callovian) deposits (Table 2).

Table 1

<p><i>Nilssonia vittaeformis</i> Prynada, <i>Nilssonia formosa</i> Vachrameeva et Vasina, <i>Podozamites</i> sp.</p>	<p><i>Nilssonia vittaeformis</i> Prynada, <i>Nilssonia formosa</i> Vachrameeva et Vasina, <i>Podozamites</i> cf. <i>lanceolatus</i> (L. et H.) var. <i>intermedius</i> Heer.</p>
<p><i>Nilssonia vittaeformis</i> Prynada, <i>Podozamites</i> sp.</p>	<p><i>Nilssonia vittaeformis</i> Prynada, <i>Nilssonia formosa</i> Vachrameeva et Vasina.</p>

Table 2

<p><i>Nilssonia vittaeformis</i> Prynada.</p>	<p><i>Nilssonia vittaeformis</i> Prynada, <i>Nilssonia formosa</i> Vachrameeva et Vasina, <i>Podozamites</i> sp.</p>
<p><i>Podozamites</i> cf. <i>lanceolatus</i> (L. et H.) var. <i>intermedius</i> Heer, <i>Nilssonia vittaeformis</i> Prynada, <i>Nilssonia formosa</i> Vachrameeva et Vasina.</p>	<p><i>Podozamites</i> cf. <i>lanceolatus</i> (L. et H.) var. <i>intermedius</i> Heer, <i>Nilssonia vittaeformis</i> Prynada, <i>Nilssonia formosa</i> Vachrameeva et Vasina.</p>
<p><i>Coniopteris hymenophylloides</i> Heer.</p>	<p><i>Coniopteris</i> cf. <i>hymenophylloides</i> Heer.</p>

Conclusions

1. Subdivision of the oil and gas-bearing complex and identification of reservoir beds based on well-logging data, together with the identification of plant impressions, made it possible to establish stratigraphic units in the studied wells No. 13 and 14 of the West Kuyi–Surgil field and in well No. 102 of the Urga field that comply with the requirements of the International Stratigraphic Code and the international ESG standard.

2. Reservoirs associated with pebble-bearing and gravelly sandstones are characterized by high porosity and permeability. The occurrence of plant impressions in siltstones at the West Kuyi–Surgil field (wells No. 13 and 14) and in well No. 102 of the Urga field confirms the Middle Jurassic age of the host rocks. This makes it possible to introduce necessary refinements and corrections to previously developed stratigraphic schemes, as well as to stratigraphic and biostratigraphic studies carried out by research institutes and scientific–production organizations.

REFERENCES

1. Abidov A.A., Abdullaev G.S., Mirkamalov Kh.Kh., Yuldashev Zh.Yu., Iskandarov M.Kh., Khudaiberganov B.I. К проблеме биостратиграфии юрских отложений Арало-Устюртского региона. *Журнал нефти и газа Узбекистана*, 2004, No. 4, pp. 10–12.
2. Jalilov G.G. Стратиграфия и флора юрских нефтегазоносных отложений Устюрта. PhD Thesis (Geology and Mineral Sciences), Tashkent, 2019, pp. 11–18.
3. Iskandarov M.Kh. Разработка методики по поискам залежей углеводородов в палеозойских и юрских отложениях центральной части Куаныш-Коскалинского вала (Республика Каракалпакстан). *Нефтегазовая геология. Теория и практика*, St. Petersburg, 2021, Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 15–21.
4. Iskandarov M.Kh., Abdullaev G.S., Mirzaev A.U., Khakimzyanov I.N., Umarov Sh.A. Научно-инновационные исследование процессов образования нефти и газа в Устюртском нефтегазоносном регионе. *Нефтяная провинция*, Bugulma, Republic of Tatarstan, Russia, 2022, No. 3 (31), pp. 23–55. DOI: 10.25689/NP.2022.3.23-55
5. Iskandarov M.Kh., Tursunova T.M., Khakimzyanov I.N., Mirzoev A.U., Umarov Sh.A., Khudaiberganov B.I. Биостратиграфическое расчленение юрских отложений Арало-Устюртского региона по растительным отпечаткам и спорово-пыльцевым комплексам. *Нефтяная провинция*, Bugulma, Republic of Tatarstan, Russia, 2022, No. 4 (32), pp. 36–64. DOI: 10.25689/NP.2022.4.36-64
6. Iskandarov M.Kh., Jalilov G.G., Khudaiberganov B.I. Биостратиграфическое расчленение юрских отложений в Арало-Устюртском регионе. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing, Germany, 2023, 105 p. (in Russian)
7. Iskandarov M.Kh., Umarov Sh.A., Khabibullaev S.S. Основы анализа локализации УВ сырья в Арало-Устюртском регионе. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing, Germany, 2024, 73 p.
8. Nazarov U.S., Sunnatov M.S., Muminov A.S., Iskandarov M.Kh., Ilyasov R.S. «Геолого-геофизическая характеристика продуктивных нефтегазоносных горизонтов терригенных юрских отложений на примере месторождения Западный Куйи Сургил» Международная научно-практическая конференция «Вопросы управления разработкой и обустройством нефтегазовых объектов», научные труды “O‘ZLITINEFTGAZ”, Issue IV–2024, Tashkent, 2025, pp. 58–68.
9. Sharafutdinova L.P. Литолого-фациальные особенности и перспективы нефтегазоносности юрских отложений Северного Устюрта. PhD Thesis (Geology and Mineral Sciences), Tashkent, 2019, pp. 9–21.
10. Khabibullaev S.S., Umarov Sh.A., Utaev K.O., Iskandarov M.Kh. Опыт и анализ применения международных стандартов в нефтегазовой геологии Узбекистана. *Информационно-экономические аспекты стандартизации и технического регулирования*, Moscow, 2025, No. 4 (85), pp. 8–18.